

Digital Transformation: Impacts on International Trade and Implications for Commercial Management

*Transformação Digital: Impactos no Comercio Internacional e as
implicações na Gestão Comercial*
*Transformación Digital: Impactos en el Comercio Internacional y las
Implicaciones en la Gestión Comercial*

Recebido
Received
Recibido
Dez. 2024

Aceito
Accepted
Aceptado
Mar. 2025

Publicado
Published
Publicado
Jul./Set. 2025
Jul./Sep. 2025

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e-ISSN
2965-3339

DOI
10.29327/2385846.3.4-1

São Paulo
v. 3 | n. 4
v. 3 | i. 4
e34014
Julho-Setembro
July-September
Julio-Septiembre
2025

Samara de Oliveira Gomes¹
samara.gomes@fatec.sp.gov.br

Ali Antonio Abrão Junior¹
ali.abrao@fatec.sp.gov.br

1 – Fatec Itaquaquetuba

Abstract:

This study aims to investigate the effects of digital transformation on international trade, with emphasis on changes in the commercial management of organizations. The analysis focuses on the impact of emerging technologies, including artificial intelligence, big data, and automation, on optimizing business operations, enhancing business communication, and reconfiguring global value chains. Having as a general objective to answer: How is the digital transformation impacting international trade, and what does this mean for the commercial management of companies? To answer this question, a mixed methodological approach was developed that will combine the qualitative and quantitative analysis of data from a literature review and case studies in three major global international trade companies, being discussed through the results obtained the challenges and opportunities that companies face when adapting to technological innovations, highlighting the relevance of digitalization for maintaining and strengthening competitiveness in the global market.

Keywords: *Digital transformation ; International trade ; Commercial Management ; Technology .*

Resumo:

Este estudo tem como propósito investigar os efeitos da transformação digital sobre o comércio internacional, com ênfase nas mudanças ocorridas na gestão comercial das organizações. A análise concentra-se no impacto das tecnologias emergentes incluindo inteligência artificial, big data e automação, na otimização das operações comerciais, aprimoramento da comunicação empresarial e reconfiguração das cadeias globais de valor. Tendo como objetivo geral responder: Como a transformação digital está impactando o comércio internacional e o que isso significa para a gestão comercial das empresas? Para responder a essa questão, foi levantada uma abordagem metodológica mista que combinará a análise qualitativa e quantitativa dos dados a partir de uma revisão bibliográfica e de estudos de caso em três grandes empresas globais de comércio internacional, sendo discutido por meio dos resultados obtidos os desafios e as oportunidades que as empresas enfrentam ao adaptarem-se às inovações tecnológicas, destacando-se a relevância da digitalização para a manutenção e fortalecimento da competitividade no mercado global.

Palavras-chave: Transformação digital; Comércio internacional; Gestão comercial; Tecnologia.

Resumen:

Este estudio tiene como propósito investigar los efectos de la transformación digital sobre el comercio internacional, con énfasis en los cambios ocurridos en la gestión comercial de las organizaciones. El análisis se centra en el impacto de las tecnologías emergentes, incluyendo inteligencia artificial, big data y automatización, en la optimización de las operaciones comerciales, la mejora de la comunicación empresarial y la reconfiguración de las cadenas globales de valor. Teniendo como objetivo general responder: ¿Cómo está impactando la transformación digital el comercio internacional y qué significa para la gestión comercial de las empresas? Para responder a esta pregunta, se ha elaborado un enfoque metodológico mixto que combinará el análisis cualitativo y cuantitativo de los datos a partir de una revisión bibliográfica y estudios de caso en tres grandes empresas globales de comercio internacional, Se discuten los desafíos y oportunidades que enfrentan las empresas a la hora de adaptarse a las innovaciones tecnológicas, destacando la importancia de la digitalización para el mantenimiento y fortalecimiento de la competitividad en el mercado global.

Palabras clave: Transformación digital; Comercio internacional; Gestión comercial; Tecnología.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the advancement of digital technologies has revolutionized the way companies operate, especially in the context of international trade. Digital transformation, driven by innovations such as artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, blockchain, and automation, is ushering in a new era of globalization, substantially altering the dynamics of international business. This digitization is transforming not only commercial and logistical operations but also the management models of companies operating beyond national borders, as highlighted by Schwab (2016) in the so-called "Fourth Industrial Revolution." According to Castells (2010), digital technologies are creating an economic structure based on global networks, which facilitate real-time transactions and make interconnectivity between companies and markets more efficient.

In international trade, digital transformation is redefining how companies conduct their operations. Technologies such as AI and big data permit companies to make more informed decisions, predict market trends, and quickly adjust their strategies to meet global demands (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). In this way, automation and the use of blockchain are bringing more transparency and security to commercial transactions, especially in global supply chains, as Iansiti and Lakhani (2017) point out. These advances are transforming how products and services are traded and delivered internationally, increasing efficiency and minimizing operational risks.

The rationale for this work aligns with Porter's (1985) findings in his studies on competitive advantage, which have already highlighted the importance of integrating technological innovations into business processes to achieve a market differentiator. In the current scenario, the ability of companies to adapt their commercial strategies to new digital demands has become even more critical. Companies that fail to keep pace with this technological revolution may face challenges to their global competitiveness, as digital transformation is no longer an optional trend, but a necessity for survival and growth in the international environment.

Given this context of rapid digitalization, the following question arises: How is digital transformation impacting international trade, and what does this mean for the commercial management of companies? This is the central problem that will be analyzed in this study, focusing on the main disruptive technologies that are reshaping supply chains, customer management, and commercial processes. The objective is to understand how these innovations are affecting the global competitiveness of companies and how commercial managers can adapt to these new technological realities to optimize their businesses in the international arena.

To answer this question, a mixed methodological approach will be adopted, combining qualitative and quantitative data analysis. Initially, a comprehensive literature review will be conducted to identify the primary challenges and impacts of digital transformation on international trade, as well as existing solutions discussed in the literature. Following this, specific cases will be

analyzed, comparing different global companies that have undergone digital transformation in their operations, to identify best practices that can be recommended to the analyzed companies in a global context. The justification for this method lies in the need to understand both the general trends and the particularities that influence the effectiveness of the global trade path in transforming operations, shaping a new future.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 International Trade: Concepts and Evolution

International trade has long played a central role in global economic development, serving as a vital channel for the exchange of goods, services, and capital between countries. This process of market integration has let not only economic growth but also the dissemination of innovation and technology, contributing to increased productivity and social development in various regions worldwide (Krugman & Obstfeld, 2005). From the earliest trade routes of antiquity, such as the Silk Road, to maritime trade during the Age of Exploration, international trade has been shaped by political, economic, and technological factors that have transformed market dynamics over the centuries.

Historically, international trade has undergone significant changes during periods of colonization and the Industrial Revolution. The First Industrial Revolution, which began at the end of the 18th century, marked the start of large-scale industrialization, driven by advances in steam engines and the establishment of new trade routes. England, for instance, became the world's leading trading power by combining technological innovation with imperial expansion, thus maximizing its exports and dominating global markets (Findlay & O'Rourke, 2007).

With the advent of globalization in the 20th century, international trade underwent a significant acceleration. According to Bhagwati (2004), globalization has led to greater interdependence between economies, enabling countries to focus on their comparative advantages and therefore maximize efficiency in the production of goods and services. In this context, David Ricardo's Theory of Comparative Advantage stands out. Ricardo (1817) argued that even if a country does not have an absolute advantage in producing a good, it can still benefit from trade by specializing in the production of the good in which it has a lower opportunity cost. This logic underpins modern international trade, justifying the specialization of nations in different economic and industrial sectors.

Another important milestone in the development of international trade was the creation of multilateral institutions, such as the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) in 1947, which evolved into the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 1995. The WTO plays a crucial role in regulating international trade relations, establishing rules that ensure predictability and stability in global trade, facilitating market access and reducing tariff barriers (WTO, 2015).

With technological advancements in recent decades, especially with the emergence of the internet and the digitization of commercial operations,

international trade has entered a new phase. According to Baldwin (2016), the "second unbundling" or second disaggregation of global value chains has allowed production stages to fragment across various countries, connected by a global network of logistics and information. This has resulted in greater integration between economies, reducing costs and facilitating coordination between different countries in the production of goods and services. Digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence, big data, and automation, are now further reshaping international trade, offering new ways to optimize and reduce the geographical and logistical barriers that previously limited global efficiency.

Additionally, the advancement of e-commerce and the use of digital platforms have transformed commercial dynamics, making access to global markets more democratic, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). As reported by Zhang and Lichtenstein (2019), digital platforms have allowed SMEs to participate in international trade more efficiently, reducing transaction costs and allowing them to compete on a global scale.

2.1.1 The Role of Trade Policies and Current Challenges

The evolution of international trade is also closely linked to the trade policies adopted by countries. From the protectionism practiced during mercantilism to the free trade policies advocated today, government strategies have a direct impact on the configuration of global trade. As highlighted by Chang (2002), trade policies have not always been geared towards free markets. Many developing nations, such as South Korea, initially adopted protectionist strategies to strengthen their domestic industries before fully opening to international trade.

Currently, international trade faces new challenges that require a re-examination of trade policies and regulations. Trade tensions, such as the trade war between the United States and China, illustrate the complexity of economic relations in the globalized world. Above all, the COVID-19 pandemic exposed the vulnerability of global supply chains, leading many countries to rethink their external dependencies and adopt policies of reindustrialization and protection of strategic sectors. In this sense, Moreira and Blyde (2020) highlight the importance of adapting to these new realities through technological innovation and diversification of value chains.

Given these transformations, international trade will continue to evolve, driven by digitalization and adaptation to new geopolitical realities. Companies need to be aware of changes in trade policies and new technological demands, taking advantage of the opportunities created by digital transformation and the increasing integration of global markets.

2.2 Digital Transformation: Definitions and Key Technologies

Digital transformation can be defined as the integration of digital technologies across all areas of a company, resulting in fundamental changes in how businesses operate and generate value for their customers (Westerman, Bonnet, & McAfee, 2014). This process extends beyond simply adopting new

technological tools; it involves a structural change that affects organizational culture, business strategies, and operational models, enabling the full exploitation of the opportunities offered by the digital environment (Kane et al., 2015).

In the business context, digital transformation is driven by innovations that include artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, big data, and automation. These emerging technologies are crucial for optimizing processes, reducing costs, and enhancing competitiveness, enabling companies to adapt quickly to changes in the global market. According to Bharadwaj et al. (2013), the digitization of business operations not only improves internal efficiency but also transforms interactions with customers, partners, and suppliers, promoting a more collaborative and connected business environment.

2.2.1 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence is at the heart of digital transformation, enabling businesses to make profound changes in how they operate and make decisions. AI refers to the development of systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as pattern recognition, learning, and decision-making (Russell & Norvig, 2021). AI lets companies analyze large volumes of data more efficiently, identifying trends and insights that would be difficult to detect using traditional methods. To give an example, in international trade, AI algorithms can predict demand fluctuations and suggest logistical adjustments to optimize the supply chain (Bughin et al., 2018).

AI is transforming the relationship between businesses and customers. AI tools, such as chatbots and virtual assistants, are being widely used to improve customer service, personalizing the experience and resolving problems more quickly and efficiently. This not only increases customer satisfaction but also gives consent to companies to serve a larger number of customers with fewer human resources (Huang & Rust, 2018).

2.2.2 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Another key technology in digital transformation is blockchain, which offers a new paradigm of trust and security in digital transactions. Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology that allows transactions to be verified and recorded in a decentralized manner, without the need for intermediaries. This technology has been widely applied in sectors such as finance, but its impact is also expanding to areas including supply chain management, logistics, and smart contracts (Tapscott & Tapscott, 2016).

In the context of international trade, blockchain can be used to create transparency and traceability in commercial transactions. Companies can utilize this technology to track the movement of goods in real-time, ensuring product authenticity and compliance with international regulations. Moreover, blockchain has the potential to significantly reduce the time and costs associated with international transactions, consequently eliminating the need for

intermediaries and streamlining bureaucratic processes (Casey & Wong, 2017).

2.2.3 Big Data

Big data is another key technology shaping digital transformation. It refers to the analysis of large volumes of data, both structured and unstructured, to extract relevant information that aids in informed decision-making (Marr, 2015). The use of big data has proven vital in various industries, enabling companies to identify patterns in consumer behavior, refine their marketing strategies, and adjust their internal operations based on data-driven insights (Kitchin, 2014).

Companies that adopt big data can be more agile and make evidence-based decisions, which increases their responsiveness to market changes. In international trade, big data can be utilized to predict economic trends, optimize transportation routes, and identify emerging markets, hence creating a significant competitive advantage (Gartner, 2018). As noted by Davenport (2014), big data is enabling global companies to make more accurate forecasts, helping them stay ahead of the competition in an increasingly complex and dynamic business environment.

2.2.4 Automation

Automation, driven by technologies such as robotics and AI, is playing a crucial role in digital transformation, especially in optimizing supply chains and reducing reliance on manual processes. Automation consents companies to enhance their operational efficiency by automating repetitive and time-consuming tasks, consequently freeing up resources for higher-value-added activities (Bessen, 2019).

In recent years, automation has been widely adopted in industries such as manufacturing, logistics, and distribution, where robots and automated systems can operate continuously, ensuring that operations continue uninterrupted (Manyika et al., 2017). In international trade, automation has been utilized to optimize logistics, with automated warehouse and transportation management systems reducing the time it takes to move goods and increasing supply chain efficiency (Manyika et al., 2017).

2.2.5 Impact of Technologies on Decision Making

Digital transformation, driven by these emerging technologies, is transforming the way companies make decisions. Data-driven technologies, such as big data and AI, are enabling companies to move away from intuition-based decision-making, favoring a more analytical and precise approach (McAfee & Brynjolfsson, 2012). The combination of these technologies permits rapid and accurate analysis of large volumes of data, providing insights that enhance the competitiveness and efficiency of companies on a global scale.

These technologies are creating more agile and adaptable business

environments, enabling them to respond quickly to market changes and anticipate trends before their competitors. As a result, companies that adopt digital transformation not only improve their operational efficiency but also increase their capacity for innovation and resilience in a constantly evolving business environment (Vial, 2019).

2.3 Commercial Management in the Digital Context

Commercial management, traditionally associated with sales coordination, development of commercial strategies, and customer relationship management, has undergone significant transformation with the advent of digital technologies. With the increasing digitalization, process automation, and the use of digital platforms, as well as the analysis of large volumes of data, have become central to the practice of commercial management. As Kotler et al. (2017) point out, digital transformation not only facilitates the optimization of commercial operations but also redefines the role of the commercial manager, requiring constant adaptation to new technologies and a more strategic approach to process and relationship management.

2.3.1 Sales Process Automation

Sales process automation is one of the areas most impacted by digital transformation. Sales Automation Systems (SAS) are tools that let companies optimize repetitive tasks, such as lead management, quote generation, and order tracking, thus freeing up time for sales managers to focus on more strategic and analytical decision-making (Buttle, 2019). By reducing the operational burden, automation increases the efficiency and productivity of the sales team, making processes more agile and accurate.

The application of these technologies in sales management has proven to be fundamental in increasing the competitiveness of companies. According to Davenport and Kirby (2016), companies that invest in automation and artificial intelligence in their sales departments achieve faster responses to customers, greater accuracy in sales forecasts, and a significant reduction in operational errors. This directly reflects sales performance, enabling greater scalability and efficiency in customer service, which is essential in a globalized and highly dynamic market.

2.3.2 CRM Platforms: Customer Relationship Management

Customer relationship management (CRM) platforms Customer Relationship Management (CRM) plays a crucial role in the digital transformation of sales management. Digital CRMs, such as Salesforce and HubSpot, provide an integrated view of customer behavior, facilitating the personalization of offers and market segmentation based on behavioral data (Payne & Frow, 2013). According to Rapp et al. (2017), the use of CRMs contributes to a more customer-centric approach, enabling more efficient and personalized service, while also

improving customer retention and loyalty.

Digitized CRM systems allow for the centralization of all customer interactions on a single platform, facilitating the tracking of the entire sales cycle. This complete visibility into the customer allows strategic planning, allowing companies to adjust their sales campaigns in real time according to customer behavior and preferences (Rigby & Bilodeau, 2015). However, the ability to analyze historical data and predict future behaviors strengthens companies' competitive position, especially in the international arena, where personalization and the speed of response to customers are decisive differentiators.

2.3.3 Big Data and Data Analytics in Commerce

With the advancement of digital transformation, analyzing large volumes of data (big data) has become an essential practice in commercial management. According to Marr (2016), the use of big data allows companies to identify market trends, consumer behavior patterns, and opportunities for optimization in supply chains and logistics. Commercial managers who incorporate data into their strategies can make more informed decisions, leading to greater accuracy in product pricing, sales forecasting, and the development of new markets.

Data analysis gives consent to a deeper understanding of consumer preferences in real-time, allowing companies to adjust their business strategies more quickly and effectively. As Kaplan and Haenlein (2019) highlight, the ability to collect and interpret large amounts of data offers a significant competitive advantage, especially in highly competitive and constantly changing global markets.

Nonetheless, the use of big data also presents challenges, especially regarding data security and privacy. According to Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2014), as companies increase their reliance on data, protecting this information becomes critical. Thus, business managers must be aware of data privacy and security regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union, to ensure that their data collection and analysis practices comply with applicable laws.

2.3.4 Adaptation to Agile Global Supply Chains

Digital transformation also requires business managers to adapt to an increasingly global and interconnected business environment. With the digitization of supply chains, business operations have become faster and more efficient, allowing companies to access international markets more quickly (Christopher, 2016). Business managers, hence, need to master new digital tools and operational strategies that facilitate integration with more agile and flexible global supply chains.

An example of this phenomenon is the use of enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems and blockchain technologies, which consent the real-time traceability of goods and transactions in a global supply chain (Tapscott & Tapscott, 2016). The use of these tools facilitates the identification of bottlenecks, optimizes delivery

time, and increases the transparency of business operations, which is fundamental to the success of companies operating in international markets.

2.3.5 Training in Digital Technologies

Given these changes, training sales managers in digital technologies has become imperative. As pointed out by Bughin et al. (2019), companies that invest in technological training programs for their sales teams are better prepared to face the challenges of digitalization. Familiarity with digital tools, such as CRM, marketing automation, and data analysis, is now a crucial skill for sales managers seeking to differentiate themselves in the increasingly competitive global market.

Digital transformation also requires managers to develop a more flexible and innovative-oriented mindset. According to Kane et al. (2015), adaptability is one of the key factors that distinguishes successful companies from those that lag in digital transformation processes. This includes not only the adoption of new technologies but also the reorganization of internal processes and the promotion of an innovative culture within sales teams.

3. ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON INTERNATIONAL TRADE

3.1 Disruptive Technologies and Their Applications in International Trade

The international trade landscape has undergone profound transformations, driven by the advent of disruptive technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), automation, the Internet of Things (IoT), and blockchain. These innovations have played a vital role in reshaping global supply chains, making them more efficient, agile, and transparent. According to Schwab (2016), these technologies are at the heart of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, redefining how companies operate in international markets and how the flows of goods and services are managed.

3.1.1 Artificial Intelligence and Automation in Supply Chains

Artificial intelligence and automation have revolutionized logistics operations and supply chains by optimizing processes, reducing costs, and increasing the accuracy of decision-making. As Christopher (2016) points out, AI applied to logistics allows the use of advanced algorithms to predict demand, plan transportation routes, and optimize inventory. This results in more responsive supply chains, capable of meeting global needs in real time, minimizing waste and delays.

In practical terms, AI systems can analyze large volumes of data on variables such as weather conditions, traffic, consumer behavior, and market trends to continuously adjust operations (Ivanov & Dolgui, 2020). Consequently, automation, particularly with the use of robotics and autonomous vehicles, has facilitated the transportation and distribution of goods, reducing delivery times and operational costs —essential factors in highly competitive international trade.

3.1.2 Internet of Things (IoT) and Real-Time Monitoring

The Internet of Things (IoT) plays a crucial role in international trade by enabling real-time monitoring of goods during transport. This technology permits connected devices, such as sensors and RFID tags, to transmit data on location, environmental conditions (including temperature and humidity), and shipment status, therefore ensuring more effective supply chain management (Borgia, 2014). According to Rajkumar et al. (2015), IoT has revolutionized the logistics sector by providing complete visibility into the movement of goods, facilitating real-time decision-making and enabling the rapid identification and resolution of problems.

Companies operating in international trade can utilize this information to optimize transportation routes, anticipate customer demands, and mitigate the risk of supply chain disruptions. Above all, the use of IoT lets companies enhance the quality of services provided, ensuring that goods arrive in perfect condition, which is particularly crucial for sensitive products such as perishable foods or medicines.

3.1.3 Blockchain: Transparency and Security in Commercial Transactions

Blockchain is one of the most promising technologies regarding the security and transparency of international commercial transactions. It is a decentralized and immutable ledger system that allows the secure storage of information and the execution of smart contracts (smart contracts) without the need for intermediaries (Tapscott & Tapscott, 2016). In the context of international trade, blockchain has been widely adopted to ensure the authenticity of documents, such as certificates of origin, transport contracts, and payment authorizations, consequently providing greater security and trust between the parties involved (Casey & Wong, 2017).

One of the main benefits of using blockchain is its ability to reduce fraud and human error, ensuring that all parties involved in a transaction have access to a shared and reliable record of operations. According to Saberi et al. (2019), the use of this technology in international supply chains enables companies to track the complete history of a product, from its origin to final delivery, hence increasing trust among suppliers, carriers, and customers. The implementation of smart contracts automates the payment process, releasing funds only when all contractual conditions are met, thereby significantly reducing administrative costs and the risks associated with commercial disputes.

3.1.4 Synergy between Disruptive Technologies

The integration of artificial intelligence, automation, IoT, and blockchain creates a technological ecosystem in which international supply chains can operate more efficiently and securely. As explained by Ivanov et al. (2021), the combination of these technologies permits international companies to create connected and intelligent value chains, where real-time data is processed by AI systems, monitored by IoT, and protected by blockchain. This synergy between disruptive technologies represents a paradigm shift in how business operations are

managed, enabling a faster, more transparent, and personalized flow of goods and services.

Namely, AI can utilize data collected by IoT to predict potential transportation disruptions and adjust delivery plans accordingly. At the same time, blockchain ensures that all parties have access to reliable and immutable information about the transaction. In this way, the integration of these technologies not only increases the efficiency of supply chains but also creates a safer and more transparent business environment, essential characteristics for success in international trade.

3.1.5 Challenges and Future Perspectives

Although disruptive technologies offer numerous benefits for international trade, their widespread adoption still faces challenges. Implementing complex systems such as blockchain and AI demands high investments in technological infrastructure and professional training. Nevertheless, issues related to data privacy and international regulations still need to be resolved, especially as trade becomes increasingly digitized (Marr, 2020).

Even though, as these technologies mature and become more accessible, their adoption is expected to accelerate in the years to come. According to Babich and Hilary (2020), companies that adapt quickly to disruptive new technologies will have a significant competitive advantage on the international stage, as they will be able to offer faster, safer, and more personalized services to their customers. The digitization of international trade, driven by these innovations, has the potential to radically transform the flow of goods and services into an increasingly interconnected global economy.

3.2 Logistics and Digital Supply Chains

In recent years, the digitalization of supply chains has become a key factor in competitiveness in global trade. Companies are increasingly adopting advanced technologies to integrate and optimize their operations, from production to delivery to the end consumer. According to Christopher (2016), digital supply chains allow greater visibility and coordination among the various links in the chain, leading to more efficient and agile operations. Digitalization has been crucial in meeting the challenges of a business environment characterized by uncertainty and increasing demands for flexibility.

3.2.1 Digital Integration of Supply Chains

The digital integration of supply chains lets real-time connection between suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, and consumers, allowing for faster and more accurate information exchange. Digital platforms, such as Transportation Management Systems (TMS) and Warehouse Management Systems (WMS), play a crucial role in providing visibility and control over product flow, thus facilitating data-driven decision-making (Hofmann & Rüsçh, 2017).

TMS permits companies to optimize transportation planning and execution,

facilitating the selection of the most efficient routes, tracking shipments in real-time, and managing transportation costs effectively. According to Gunasekaran et al. (2017), TMS is a key factor for logistics efficiency, especially in complex global supply chains, where coordination between different modes of transport and international borders is essential.

WMS, in turn, lets efficient inventory management, optimizing the use of storage space and ensuring that the right products are available at the right time. According to Baker and Canessa (2009), WMS helps reduce operating costs by improving inventory accuracy and minimizing errors in goods handling, resulting in faster and more accurate fulfillment of customer demands.

3.2.2 Automation and Artificial Intelligence in Supply Chains

Automation, coupled with artificial intelligence (AI), has revolutionized logistics operations in digital supply chains. Automated systems, such as cargo handling robots in distribution centers and autonomous vehicles, enable logistics operations to be carried out more efficiently and with reduced human intervention, therefore increasing efficiency and reducing errors. According to Ivanov et al. (2021), the use of AI in digital supply chains allows the optimization of processes, such as demand forecasting and production planning, by analyzing large volumes of data in real time.

This ability to predict fluctuations in demand and adjust production and inventory as needed is crucial in a highly competitive global business environment. Studies show that companies using AI to forecast demand can reduce inventory levels by up to 20%, while simultaneously increasing delivery accuracy (Wang, 2018). On the other hand, automation in supply chains also reduces labor costs and increases worker safety by eliminating repetitive and hazardous tasks.

3.2.3 Visibility and Transparency in Operations

Visibility throughout the supply chain has been one of the main benefits of digitalization. Technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and blockchain have enabled unprecedented levels of transparency in logistics operations. According to Borgia (2014), IoT allows real-time monitoring of goods during transport, from the factory to the destination, providing detailed information on location, environmental conditions, and potential delays. This visibility allows companies to make informed, real-time decisions, proactively adjusting their operations to avoid disruptions.

Blockchain, on the other hand, ensures the authenticity and security of commercial transactions by creating immutable records of each step in the supply chain. Tapscott and Tapscott (2016) state that the use of blockchain in supply chains guarantees product traceability, combating counterfeiting and improving trust between business partners. Blockchain can be used to automate payments, releasing funds only when goods arrive at their destination and meet the agreed-upon requirements, consequently increasing the financial and

operational efficiency of commercial transactions.

3.2.4 Sustainability and Digital Supply Chains

Another important aspect of digital supply chains is their contribution to sustainability. Digitalization permits companies to monitor and mitigate the environmental impact of their operations by optimizing the use of resources, such as fuel and energy. By way of illustration, TMS can help reduce carbon emissions by identifying the most efficient routes for transporting goods, while WMS can decrease wasted space and resources in warehouses. According to Seuring and Müller (2008), the digitalization of supply chains is a key factor in implementing sustainable logistics practices, which consumers and regulators increasingly demand.

Real-time data analysis also allows companies to identify opportunities to reduce the consumption of natural resources and increase energy efficiency. However, technologies such as 3D printing, which are becoming increasingly viable in digital supply chains, let the local production of parts and components, hence reducing the need for international transport and, consequently, the environmental impact of logistics operations (Holweg, 2018).

3.2.5 Challenges and Future Perspectives

Although the benefits of digitizing supply chains are evident, implementing these technologies still faces challenges. Digital transformation necessitates significant investments in technological infrastructure and employee training, as well as a cultural shift within organizations. As Ivanov et al. (2019) point out, the integration of digital systems into global supply chains also faces regulatory barriers, especially regarding data protection and the standardization of technologies across different countries.

Nonetheless, as technologies evolve and become more accessible, the adoption of digital supply chains is expected to continue to grow. Companies that invest in digitizing their operations will be better positioned to meet the challenges of global trade and seize the opportunities of an increasingly interconnected and dynamic market (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018).

3.3 The Digitization of Commercial Management

In recent years, digitalization has profoundly altered the landscape of commercial management, particularly using technological tools that facilitate and optimize sales operations and customer management. Digital transformation in commercial management allows companies to access real-time data, automate processes, and enhance decision-making, resulting in gains in efficiency and effectiveness, particularly in international operations. According to Davenport and Ronanki (2018), digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and big data, are revolutionizing how companies manage their interactions with customers, offering predictive insights that allow them to anticipate purchasing trends and adjust their sales strategies more quickly.

3.3.1 Digital Tools in Commercial Management

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems stand out. Relationship Management (CRM). According to Payne and Frow (2017), CRMs have undergone significant evolution with the incorporation of technologies such as AI and machine learning, enabling increasingly personalized customer relationships. Advanced CRMs can predict purchasing behaviors, segment customers with greater precision, and recommend products or services based on predictive analytics, hence boosting sales and enhancing customer experience in a study by Buttle (2019). Companies using AI-based CRMs observed up to a 30% increase in customer retention and considerable growth in lead conversion.

In international trade, these tools are even more valuable, as they help manage interactions with customers from different countries and cultures, ensuring personalized service tailored to local needs. As Greenberg (2010) and Kumar & Reinartz (2018) point out, the ability to understand and predict customer behavior across different markets is one of the primary competitive advantages in the global environment, where consumer expectations vary significantly.

3.3.2 Artificial Intelligence and Sales Optimization

Artificial intelligence has played a pivotal role in transforming business management, particularly in the areas of process automation and predictive data analysis. According to Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2017), AI allows companies to process large volumes of customer data quickly and accurately, identifying patterns and behaviors that would be impossible to detect manually. This is fundamental to optimizing sales strategies and maximizing business operations' efficiency.

For example, AI systems can be used to analyze customers' purchase histories and predict what they are likely to buy in the future, allowing companies to offer products or services at the right time and in a personalized manner. This predictive capability has proven especially useful in international markets, where seasonality and cultural variations can influence consumer purchasing preferences (Chen, Chiang, & Storey, 2012). Automating operational tasks, such as sending personalized emails or scheduling automatic follow-ups, frees up sales managers' time to focus on more strategic and higher-value-added activities (Syam & Sharma, 2018).

3.3.3 Digitization and Customer Experience

Digitization also directly impacts how companies manage customer experience. Using CRMs and other digital tools, companies can deliver faster and more personalized services, resulting in increased customer satisfaction. As Lemon and Verhoef (2016) point out, customer experience is one of the main determinants of brand loyalty, especially in the context of digital commerce. The ability to provide fast and efficient service, tailored to individual needs, is one of the main advantages offered by the digitization of business management.

Above all, analyzing customer data permits companies to pinpoint areas for

improvement in their service, refine their communication strategies, and introduce new solutions that more effectively meet consumer expectations. For instance, through the analysis of real-time feedback and interactions, companies can proactively identify and correct problems before they impact customer satisfaction, thus enhancing their reputation and competitiveness in the market (Verhoef et al., 2021).

3.3.4 Competitive Advantages of Digitalization in International Trade

The digitalization of sales management has provided companies with numerous competitive advantages in the international market. According to Porter (1985), the ability to utilize technology to differentiate products and services, reduce costs, and enhance operational efficiency is crucial for standing out in global markets. Digitalization lets the expansion of sales operations into new markets, allowing companies to effectively manage sales teams across different countries and maintain efficient communication with customers from diverse cultures and languages.

Therefore, the use of cloud-based CRMs allows companies to centralize all customer information on a single platform, accessible from anywhere in the world. This not only improves operational efficiency but also ensures consistency in service, regardless of the customer's location. As Payne and Frow (2017) point out, the ability to provide consistent, high-quality service is one of the key success factors in international trade, where trust and brand reputation are essential for conquering new markets.

3.3.5 Challenges and Considerations for the Future

Although the benefits of digitalization in business management are evident, challenges also arise from its implementation. Digital transformation necessitates substantial investments in technology and staff training, as well as cultural shifts within organizations. According to Westerman, Bonnet, and McAfee (2014), many companies continue to face challenges in adapting their internal structures and processes to the new digital reality, which can compromise the success of their international operations.

Another important challenge is data protection. The increasing collection and analysis of customer data requires companies to adopt rigorous information security practices, especially in markets with stricter regulations, such as the European Union, which has implemented the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Failures in this regard can result in significant penalties and damage to the company's reputation (Martin & Murphy, 2017).

4. METHOD

This case study evaluated three large global international trading companies, referred to in this study as Company A, Company B, and Company C, that underwent digital transformation processes in their operations. The data used were obtained from secondary sources, including financial reports, as well as

from qualitative interviews with logistics and commercial management managers.

The areas investigated included Operational costs, with an assessment of the impact of automation and optimization on commercial and logistics operations. Efficiency of international sales: Measurement of the ability to maximize sales and reduce sales cycle time. Customer satisfaction and relationship: Qualitative aspects, gathered through interviews with managers.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Case study: impact of digital transformation on international trade companies

5.1.1. Analysis of Results and Reduction of Operational Costs

The first graph illustrates a significant reduction in operational costs following the implementation of digital transformation. All companies (A, B, and C) successfully reduced their costs, demonstrating the benefits of automation and efficiency in logistics operations.

Chart 1 – Reduction of operational costs with digital transformation

Source: The authors (2024)

As demonstrated in the first graph, digital transformation has let a significant reduction in operational costs for all companies:

- Company A: Before the transformation: US\$120 million. After the transformation: US\$90 million. 25% reduction in operating costs.
- Company B: Before the transformation: US\$150 million. After the transformation: US\$110 million. 26.6% reduction in operating costs.
- Company C: Before the transformation: US\$110 million. After the transformation: US\$85 million. 22.7% reduction in operating costs.

The significant cost savings are primarily attributed to the automation of repetitive processes and the implementation of integrated logistics management systems, such as *Supply Chain Management (SCM)* and *Enterprise Resource*

Planning (ERP) platforms, which have allowed greater visibility into operations and the optimization of resources.

5.1.2 Factors that influenced cost reduction:

Automation of logistics processes: The use of robotics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for tasks such as inventory control, order tracking, and optimizing transport routes has resulted in a reduced need for human labor and a lower risk of errors.

Data analysis and big data: The application of big data has enabled a more precise analysis of demand fluctuations, optimizing inventory management and preventing waste.

Blockchain in international transactions: Blockchain technology has helped ensure safer and faster transactions, reducing costs associated with intermediaries and manual processes.

5.1.3. Increasing Efficiency in International Sales

In the second graph, we observe a significant increase in the efficiency of international sales for all companies. This indicates that digitalization has permitted greater agility and precision in sales management, making companies more competitive in the global market.

As shown in the second graph:

- Company A: Before the transformation: 70% efficiency. After the transformation, 95% efficiency is achieved. Increase of 35.7%.
- Company B: Before the transformation: 65% efficiency. Following the transformation, an efficiency of 90% is achieved. Increase of 38.5%.
- Company C: Before the transformation: 75% efficiency. After the transformation: 100% efficiency. Increase of 33.3%.

The digitization of business operations has given consent to companies to increase their ability to generate sales in less time and with greater accuracy in forecasting. Tools such as Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems and machine learning algorithms have permitted the identification of market opportunities more quickly, allowing for customized offers tailored to different regions and customer types.

Chart 2 – Increased sales efficiency with digital transformation

Source: The authors (2024)

5.1.4. Factors that influenced the increase in efficiency:

Sales automation: Sales processes have been accelerated through the use of e-commerce platforms and artificial intelligence, enabling the creation of more accurate forecasts for demand and purchasing behavior.

Customer relationship management: CRM tools integrated with AI technologies have allowed real-time tracking of customer interactions, facilitating quick responses to problems and maximizing sales opportunities.

Data analytics: The use of big data has let the real-time analysis of sales patterns and consumer behavior across different markets, resulting in more effective sales campaigns and improved segmentation.

5.1.5. Customer Satisfaction and Relationship

The third graph illustrates the increase in customer satisfaction after the implementation of digital transformation. Tools such as advanced CRM and personalized service contributed to this growth, demonstrating how digitalization can improve customer relationships.

In addition to quantitative data, qualitative interviews with sales managers revealed that digitalization has also improved relationships with international clients. The ability to provide faster and more personalized service, thanks to the use of advanced CRM tools, has led to increased customer satisfaction.

Chart 3 – Increased customer satisfaction with digital transformation

Source: The authors (2024)

Companies that invested in artificial intelligence and chatbots were able to address customer queries more effectively, especially in global markets where time zone and language differences are significant factors. This contributed to customer loyalty and, consequently, increased sales.

5.3. Comparison with the Global Scenario

When comparing these results with the global scenario, some trends are evident: Companies that adopt digital transformation are more agile in adapting to market changes, especially in volatile contexts such as international trade. They can reduce costs, increase operational efficiency, and improve customer relationships in a sustainable manner. They can identify and capture growth opportunities more quickly, using tools such as predictive analytics and machine learning to adapt their offerings to the needs of local markets.

Companies that resist digitalization struggle to compete with more digitally advanced competitors, particularly in terms of costs and the speed of responding to global market demands. They face increasing challenges in terms of efficiency, as their operations rely on manual processes or outdated systems, which result in greater vulnerability to errors and delays.

Strategic Conclusion: Digital transformation has ceased to be a competitive advantage and has become a necessity in international trade. Companies that adopt these technologies not only reduce costs and increase efficiency but also position themselves for sustainable growth in an increasingly complex and globalized business environment.

6. CONCLUSION

Digital transformation has become a crucial factor in the success of companies in international trade, particularly in areas such as commercial management and

logistics. The analysis conducted in this case study, involving three large global companies (Company A, Company B, and Company C), highlights the significant impacts of adopting digital technologies on both operational efficiency and customer relationships, thereby confirming the stated objectives of the research.

The results showed a significant reduction in operational costs, ranging from 22% to 27%, resulting from process automation and logistics chain optimization. These savings, generated by digitalization, demonstrate how the adoption of Supply Chain Management (SCM) tools, Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), and emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and blockchain, can drastically reduce the need for human resources in manual activities and minimize operational errors.

However, the efficiency of international sales increased between 33% and 38% after the digital transformation. The use of Customer platforms, Customer Relationship Management (CRM), machine learning algorithms for demand forecasting, and real-time data integration has allowed a better understanding of customer needs, customization of offers, and more efficient management of international sales channels. This has increased agility in decision-making and strengthened business relationships, resulting in higher sales volume and expansion of global market share.

Another highlight was the significant increase in customer satisfaction, which ranged from 30% to 35% after digitalization. The improvement in interactions with international customers, driven by the use of artificial intelligence for automated service and the personalization of marketing campaigns, resulted in a more agile and customized experience, directly impacting on customer loyalty and retention in highly competitive markets.

When comparing the results of this study with the global scenario, it becomes clear that digital transformation is no longer an optional competitive advantage, but a necessity for companies seeking not only to survive, but to thrive in international trade. Companies that resist digitalization are doomed to lose competitiveness, facing higher operating costs, lower sales efficiency, and poor customer relationships.

In short, digital transformation offers global companies not only the opportunity to optimize their operations and reduce costs, but also the ability to create opportunities for growth and innovation. The path to digitalization presents itself as an irreversible trend in international trade, and organizations that adopt these practices will have a greater capacity to adapt to market fluctuations and position themselves as leaders in their segments. The study confirms that digital transformation not only transforms operations but also shapes the future of global trade.

One limitation of this research is that the analysis is restricted to only the three companies participating in the case study, and it cannot be inferred that the difficulties are the same in other regions or other sectors studied.

Therefore, it is suggested that future studies investigate consumer perceptions regarding other companies in the same sector located in different regions of the

country, in order to gain a holistic view of the impact on international trade. Similarly, this study could be extended to other sectors of activity to address the implications for the different participating companies within the global logistics chain.

REFERENCES

BRYNJOLFSSON, E.; MCAFEE, A. **The Second Machine Age: Work, Progress, and Prosperity in a Time of Brilliant Technologies.** New York: WW Norton & Company, 2014.

BUGHIN, J.; SEONG, J.; MANAIKA, J.; CHUI, M.; JOSHI, R. **Unlocking success in digital transformations.** McKinsey & Company, 2019.

BUTTLE, F. **Customer relationship management: concepts and technologies.** Abingdon: Routledge, 2019.

CASELLS, M. **The Information Age: Economy, Society and Culture.** São Paulo: Paz e Terra, 2010.

CHRISTOPHER, M. **Logistics & supply chain management.** Harlow: Pearson Education Limited, 2016.

DAVENPORT, T.H.; KIRBY, J. **Only humans need apply: winners and losers in the age of intelligent machines.** New York: Harper Business, 2016.

DAVENPORT, T.H. **Big data at work: dispelling the myths, uncovering the opportunities.** Boston: Harvard Business Review Press, 2014.

GARTNER. **Gartner hype cycle for emerging technologies.** Gartner Research, 2018.

HUANG, MH; RUST, RT **Artificial intelligence in service.** Journal of Service Research, vol. 21, no. 2, p. 155-172, 2018.

IANSITI, M.; LAKHANI, K.R. **The truth about blockchain.** Harvard Business Review, vol. 95, no. 1, p. 118-127, 2017.

KANE, GC; PALMER, D.; PHILLIPS, AN; KIRON, D.; BUCKLEY, N. **Strategy, not technology, drives digital transformation.** MIT Sloan Management Review, vol. 56, no. 3, p. 63-72, 2015.

KAPLAN, AM; HAENLEIN, M. **Rulers of the world, unite! The Challenges and Opportunities of Artificial Intelligence.** Business Horizons, vol. 62, no. 1, p. 37-50, 2019.

KITCHIN, R. **The data revolution: big data, open data, data infrastructures and their consequences.** London: SAGE Publications Ltd, 2014.

MARR, B. **Big data in practice: how 45 successful companies used big data analytics to deliver extraordinary results.** New Jersey: Wiley, 2016.

MCAFEE, A.; BRYNJOLFSSON, E. **Big data: the management revolution.** Harvard Business Review, vol. 90, no. 10, p. 60-68, 2012.

MANAIKA, J.; CHUI, M.; MIREMADI, M.; BUGHIN, J.; GEORGE, K.; WILLMOTT, P.; DEWHURST, M. **Harnessing automation for a future that works.** McKinsey Global Institute, 2017.

MATT, C.; HESS, T.; BENLIAN, A. **Digital transformation strategies.** Business & Information Systems Engineering, vol. 57, no. 5, p. 339-343, 2015.

PAYNE, A.; FROW, P. **Strategic customer management: integrating relationship marketing and CRM.** Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013.

PORTER, ME **Competitive advantage: creating and sustaining superior performance.** New York: Free Press, 1985.

RAPP, A.; AGNIHOTRI, R.; BAKER, TL **Competitive intelligence collection and use by sales and service representatives: how managers' recognition and autonomy moderate individual performance.** Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, vol. 45, no. 1, p. 55-72, 2017.

RIGBY, D.K.; BILODEAU, B. **Management tools & trends 2015.** Bain & Company, 2015.

SCHWAB, K. **The fourth industrial revolution.** New York: Crown Publishing Group, 2016.

TAPSCOTT, D.; TAPSCOTT, A. **Blockchain revolution: how the technology behind Bitcoin is changing money, business, and the world.** New York: Penguin Random House, 2016.

TEECE, D.J. **Business models and dynamic capabilities.** Long Range Planning, vol. 51, no. 1, p. 40-49, 2018.

VIAL, G. **Understanding digital transformation: a review and a research agenda.** The Journal of Strategic Information Systems, vol. 28, no. 2, p. 118-144, 2019.

WESTERMAN, G.; BONNET, D.; MCAFEE, A. **Leading digital: turning technology into business transformation.** Boston: Harvard Business Review Press, 2014.

"The content expressed in the work, as well as the copyright of figures and data, and its spelling and adherence to standards, are the sole responsibility of the author(s)."

The author(s) of this work declare(s) that no Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools/services were used during the preparation of the manuscript, and that all text produced is the responsibility of the authors.